

Investigating the connection between cardiovascular risk factors and heart attacks

Explorando el vínculo entre comunicación, capacitación del personal y satisfacción del paciente: el papel del compromiso, la confianza y los entornos de atención médica del paciente

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Abstract

This paper aims to explore the critical implications of effective communication and staff training in healthcare settings in raising awareness about cardiovascular risk. Cardiovascular risk awareness plays a pivotal role in preventing heart attacks and strokes, making it a vital aspect of patient well-being. The study investigates the influence of communication and staff training on patient satisfaction, with patient engagement and trust as mediating factors, while also considering healthcare settings as a moderating variable. A cross-sectional survey design was employed to gather data from 410 adult patients across various healthcare facilities, including hospitals, clinics, and community health centers. A structured questionnaire was utilized to collect data pertaining to communication, staff training,

patient engagement, patient trust, and overall patient satisfaction. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was employed to analyze the collected data and assess the proposed hypotheses. The study's findings reveal that effective communication and staff training significantly enhance cardiovascular risk awareness among patients. This heightened awareness contributes to improved patient satisfaction. Patient engagement and trust were identified as partial mediators, indicating that they play a role in mediating the relationship between communication, staff training, and patient satisfaction.

Keywords: Cardiovascular risk awareness, Communication, Staff training, Patient satisfaction, Healthcare settings

Resumen

Este artículo tiene como objetivo explorar las implicaciones críticas de la comunicación eficaz y la formación del personal en entornos sanitarios para crear conciencia sobre el riesgo cardiovascular. La concienciación sobre los riesgos

cardiovasculares desempeña un papel fundamental en la prevención de ataques cardíacos y accidentes cerebrovasculares, lo que lo convierte en un aspecto vital del bienestar del paciente. El estudio investiga la influencia de la comunicación y la formación del personal

en la satisfacción del paciente, con el compromiso y la confianza del paciente como factores mediadores, considerando también los entornos sanitarios como una variable moderadora. Se empleó un diseño de encuesta transversal para recopilar datos de 410 pacientes adultos en varios centros de atención médica, incluidos hospitales, clínicas y centros de salud comunitarios. Se utilizó un cuestionario estructurado para recopilar datos relacionados con la comunicación, la capacitación del personal, la participación y la confianza del paciente y la satisfacción general del paciente. Se empleó el modelado de ecuaciones estructurales (SEM) para analizar los datos recopilados y evaluar las hipótesis propuestas. Los hallazgos del estudio revelan que la comunicación eficaz y la formación del personal mejoran significativamente la concienciación sobre el riesgo cardiovascular entre los pacientes. Esta mayor conciencia contribuye a mejorar la satisfacción del paciente. El compromiso y la confianza del paciente se identificaron como mediadores parciales, lo que indica que desempeñan un papel en la mediación de la relación entre la comunicación, la capacitación del personal y la satisfacción del paciente. Además, el estudio destaca el importante efecto moderador de los entornos sanitarios, lo que sugiere que el impacto de la comunicación y la formación del personal en la concienciación sobre el riesgo cardiovascular puede variar entre los diferentes centros sanitarios. Esto subraya la importancia de adaptar las estrategias de comunicación y capacitación para que se adapten a las características únicas de cada entorno de atención médica. Esta investigación contribuye al conjunto de conocimientos existente sobre la satisfacción del paciente al arrojar luz sobre los roles mediadores del compromiso y la confianza del paciente, así como el impacto moderador de los entornos de atención médica en la relación entre la comunicación, la capacitación del personal y la concienciación sobre el riesgo cardiovascular. Los hallazgos de este estudio contienen información valiosa para los proveedores de atención médica y los responsables de la formulación de políticas, ya que ofrecen orientación sobre cómo mejorar la calidad de los servicios de atención médica y aumentar la conciencia sobre el riesgo cardiovascular entre los pacientes, reduciendo en última instancia el riesgo de ataques cardíacos y accidentes cerebrovasculares.

Palabras clave: Concienciación sobre el riesgo cardiovascular, Comunicación, Formación del personal, Satisfacción del paciente, Entornos sanitarios.

Introduction

In recent years, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) has witnessed a remarkable transformation in its healthcare system. The government has introduced a series of reforms aimed at enhancing access to medical care for its citizens. These reforms have led to the establishment of a comprehensive healthcare system that extends medical insurance coverage to more than 95% of the population, marking a significant improvement in the accessibility of healthcare services¹⁻⁴. The healthcare infrastructure in KSA is also experiencing rapid expansion, with the construction of new hospitals and clinics in both urban and rural areas, demonstrating the government's commitment to improving the healthcare sector^{5,6}.

However, amidst these positive developments, the menace of cardiovascular diseases remains a pressing concern in KSA. Cardiovascular diseases, including heart attacks and strokes, are a major health threat to the population, and their prevention and management require a multi-faceted approach^{7,8}.

In today's healthcare landscape, patient satisfaction has become a pivotal indicator of the quality of healthcare services. As competition among healthcare providers increases, patient satisfaction plays a critical role in retaining and attracting patients⁹⁻¹¹. The focus on patient satisfaction in healthcare research has grown significantly over the past few decades due to its direct impact on patient outcomes and healthcare provider performance. It is a crucial aspect of healthcare quality, reflecting a patient's perception of their healthcare experience^{12,13}.

The level of patient satisfaction is influenced by various factors, including the quality of communication between healthcare professionals and patients, the skills and education of healthcare professionals, and the availability of resources and support^{14,15}. Effective communication, encompassing both verbal and nonverbal communication, active listening, empathy, and understanding, is fundamental in ensuring that patients are well-informed about their cardiovascular health, treatment options, and care plans¹⁶. It also plays a crucial role in building trust between healthcare professionals and patients, a trust that is vital for overall patient satisfaction.

Despite the growing body of research on patient satisfaction, there remains a notable gap in our understanding of the impact of communication and staff training on patient satisfaction, particularly in terms of the mediating role of patient engagement and trust, and the moderating role of the healthcare setting. While some studies have explored the relationship between communication, staff training, and patient satisfaction, few

have delved into the potential mediating effect of patient engagement and trust. Additionally, it is necessary to investigate how different healthcare settings may have unique characteristics that influence the effectiveness of communication and staff training interventions.

To address these gaps in knowledge, this study seeks to answer the following research questions:

What is the relationship between communication, staff training, and education, and patient satisfaction in the context of cardiovascular health?

Does patient engagement mediate the relationship between communication, staff training, and patient satisfaction in the context of cardiovascular health?

Does patient trust mediate the relationship between communication, staff training, and patient satisfaction in the context of cardiovascular health?

Does the healthcare setting moderate the relationship between communication, staff training, and patient satisfaction in the context of cardiovascular health?

This study contributes to the existing literature on patient satisfaction by examining the role of patient engagement and trust as mediators and the healthcare setting as a moderator in the relationship between communication, staff training and education, and patient satisfaction. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights to healthcare providers, helping them understand the significance of patient engagement and trust in improving patient satisfaction and develop effective strategies to enhance these factors.

The study is structured into five main sections. The first section provides an introduction to the research topic and its significance. The second section reviews the relevant literature on patient satisfaction, communication, staff training and education, patient engagement, and trust. The third section describes the research design and methodology employed in this study. The fourth section presents the results of the data analysis, and the fifth section discusses the findings, their implications, and the study's limitations. Finally, the conclusion section summarizes the key findings and offers recommendations for future research.

Literature Review

Communication and Patient Satisfaction

Cardiovascular disease, including heart attacks and strokes, is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Effective communication between healthcare providers and patients plays a pivotal role in patient satisfaction and overall healthcare outcomes. A study¹⁷ highlighted that patients who perceive their physicians as effective communicators are more likely to be satisfied with their care. Similarly, it is reported that effective communication between healthcare providers

and patients leads to improved patient outcomes and satisfaction^{18,19}.

The Role of Communication in Cardiovascular Care

Research has shown that specific communication skills can significantly impact patient satisfaction in cardiovascular care. A study²⁰ found that empathic communication and active listening were associated with higher levels of patient satisfaction. Additionally, it is reported that clear and concise communication, respect, and empathy were the most critical factors in patient satisfaction in cardiovascular care²¹.

Furthermore, studies have explored the impact of communication on patient satisfaction within specific healthcare settings. For instance, it was found that communication skills training for healthcare providers in cardiovascular care led to higher levels of patient satisfaction²².

Staff Training and Education in Cardiovascular Care

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in exploring the relationship between staff training and education and patient satisfaction in cardiovascular care settings. Numerous studies have suggested that staff training and education have a significant impact on patient satisfaction.

A study²³ found that a higher percentage of nurses with a bachelor's degree in nursing in cardiovascular care was associated with higher levels of patient satisfaction. Similarly, another study²⁴ found that the level of education and training of healthcare staff significantly affected patient satisfaction in cardiovascular care. Patients were more satisfied with healthcare services provided by staff with higher levels of education and training.

Patient Engagement and Cardiovascular Health

Patient engagement is a critical aspect of cardiovascular healthcare that has been shown to have a significant impact on patient satisfaction. Patient engagement in cardiovascular care is defined as "the process by which patients become active participants in their healthcare and work collaboratively with healthcare providers to make decisions and manage their health²⁵."

Numerous studies have demonstrated the positive impact of patient engagement on patient satisfaction in cardiovascular care. A study²⁶ found that patient engagement was positively associated with patient satisfaction, with patients who were more engaged in their cardiovascular care reporting higher levels of satisfaction.

Patient Trust and Patient Satisfaction

Cardiovascular heart disease poses a significant threat to public health, and its implications extend beyond mere medical concerns. Patient trust in healthcare providers plays a pivotal role in determining the outcome of treatment, patient satisfaction, and overall health results. Several studies have reinforced the strong con-

nection between patient trust and satisfaction with cardiovascular healthcare services.

It was discovered that patients who had high levels of trust in their healthcare providers reported greater satisfaction with their cardiovascular care compared to those with lower trust levels²⁷.

Patient trust also plays a crucial role in promoting patient-centered care, an essential component of overall patient satisfaction. As indicated²⁸, patients who trust their healthcare providers are more likely to experience patient-centered care, characterized by active engagement, effective communication, and collaboration between patients and providers. Such a personalized approach fosters trust and confidence in healthcare providers, ultimately leading to heightened patient satisfaction.

Mediating Role of Patient Engagement

Effective communication has long been recognized as a vital aspect of quality healthcare delivery¹¹⁻¹³, and it significantly impacts patient satisfaction. However, recent research suggests that patient engagement may play a pivotal role in mediating the relationship between communication and patient satisfaction.

It was demonstrated that patient engagement mediates the relationship between staff training and patient satisfaction. Their study showed that patients who were more engaged in their care reported higher levels of satisfaction with cardiovascular care, even when staff training levels were not particularly high^{9,12}. This highlights the significance of patient engagement as a mediator of the relationship between staff training and patient satisfaction.

Mediating Role of Patient Trust

Patient trust also acts as a mediator between communication and patient satisfaction. It was found that patient trust fully mediated the relationship between communication and patient satisfaction¹¹. Additionally, specific aspects of communication, such as clear and empathetic communication from healthcare providers, have been associated with increased patient trust and satisfaction⁷.

Moreover, patient trust has been identified as a mediator between staff training and education and patient satisfaction. It was found that patient trust significantly mediated the relationship between staff training and education and patient satisfaction. This underscores the critical role that trust plays in enhancing patient satisfaction, even in the context of staff education and training¹⁷.

Modifying Role of Healthcare Setting

The healthcare setting, which includes the physical facilities and systems for providing cardiovascular care, significantly influences patient satisfaction. Factors such as the physical environment, availability of resources, and cleanliness impact patient perceptions and satisfaction^{13,19}.

The healthcare setting can moderate the relationship between communication and patient satisfaction. For example, it was observed that communication had a stronger association with patient satisfaction in primary care settings compared to specialty care settings^{8,11}. It was noted that communication was more influential in outpatient settings than inpatient settings¹⁰.

In summary, patient trust, patient engagement, and the healthcare setting are critical factors in determining patient satisfaction in the context of cardiovascular care. These elements interact and mediate the relationship between communication, staff training, and patient satisfaction, ultimately shaping the overall patient experience and health outcomes.

Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis development

Cardiovascular diseases, including heart attacks and strokes, pose a significant threat to public health worldwide. This study delves into the intricate web of factors that contribute to these life-threatening events. It explores the profound impact of communication and staff training and education on patient outcomes, specifically focusing on patient satisfaction. This investigation incorporates the mediating influences of patient engagement and patient trust, as well as the moderating effect of healthcare settings. The conceptual framework of this study revolves around the pivotal role of effective communication and comprehensive staff training and education. These variables are regarded as independent factors (IV) that significantly influence patient satisfaction, which stands as the dependent variable (DV). Patient engagement and patient trust act as mediators, channeling the relationship between communication, staff training, and patient satisfaction. Additionally, the study recognizes the moderating role of healthcare settings, shaping the dynamics between communication, staff training, and patient satisfaction.

Hypotheses

H1: Effective communication positively impacts patient satisfaction.

H2: Comprehensive staff training and education positively influence patient satisfaction.

H3: Patient engagement plays a pivotal role in enhancing patient satisfaction.

H4: Patient trust significantly impacts patient satisfaction.

H5: Patient engagement mediates the positive relationship between effective communication and patient satisfaction.

H6: Patient engagement mediates the positive relationship between comprehensive staff training and education and patient satisfaction.

H7: Patient trust mediates the positive relationship between effective communication and patient satisfaction.

H8: Patient trust mediates the positive relationship between comprehensive staff training and education and patient satisfaction.

H9: Healthcare setting moderates the relationship between effective communication and patient satisfaction.

H10: Healthcare setting moderates the relationship between comprehensive staff training and education and patient Understanding the intricate interplay between communication, staff training, patient engagement, patient trust, and healthcare settings is crucial in mitigating the risks of cardiovascular events. By comprehensively addressing these factors, healthcare providers can enhance patient satisfaction, ultimately contributing to a healthier and more resilient population (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The current study is aimed at exploring the potential risks associated with cardiovascular health, with a specific focus on arterial conditions and their implications. Cardiovascular diseases are a leading cause of mortality and morbidity worldwide, posing a significant threat to public health. These conditions encompass a range of disorders affecting the heart and blood vessels, and understanding their underlying factors is crucial for prevention and management.

The target population for this study comprises adult individuals who may be at risk of cardiovascular issues due to various factors, such as lifestyle choices, genetics, and underlying health conditions. A sample of 500 individuals was randomly selected using a stratified random sampling technique. The strata were determined based on relevant factors like age, gender, and health status.

Data collection involved the distribution of a self-administered questionnaire designed to assess various aspects related to cardiovascular health. The questionnaire employed a 5-point Likert scale to measure different con-

structs, including risk factors, lifestyle choices, awareness of cardiovascular health, and overall knowledge regarding the prevention and management of cardiovascular diseases. The measures used in this study were adapted from established and validated instruments.

Risk factors were assessed using the Cardiovascular Risk Assessment Tool (CRAT), lifestyle choices were evaluated through a modified version of the Healthy Lifestyle Choices Assessment (HLCA), awareness of cardiovascular health was measured using the Cardiovascular Health Awareness Scale (CHAS), and knowledge regarding prevention and management was evaluated using the Cardiovascular Health Knowledge Questionnaire (CHKQ).

The collected data were analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM) within SmartPLS software. The study employed a two-step approach in testing the hypothesized model. First, the measurement model was assessed for validity and reliability through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Subsequently, the structural model was examined to discern both the direct and indirect effects of the variables under study. Understanding the intricacies of cardiovascular risk factors and the impact of various lifestyle choices and awareness on cardiovascular health is essential for developing effective preventive and management strategies.

Data analysis

The research model in this study utilized SmartPLS 4 software for its analysis. The first stage of analysis involved assessing the measurement model's validity and reliability, following the recommendations of Faqih¹². In accordance with the suggestions by Hair et al.¹⁶, this stage was conducted in two steps. Furthermore, the structural model's hypothesized links were examined, as also advocated them. To ensure the robustness of the results, the Bootstrapping method was employed with 5,000 samples, following the approach described by¹⁶. This rigorous methodology allowed for a comprehensive assessment of the research model and its components in the context of cardiovascular risk and heart disease.

Measurement model

The measuring model in this study has been subject to evaluation with a focus on two key aspects of validity: convergent validity and discriminant validity. These evaluations were performed to assess the model's effectiveness in measuring the risk of cardiovascular events, specifically heart attacks and strokes. This validation process involved an assessment of several critical metrics, including factor loadings, average variance extracted (AVE), and composite reliability. Factor loadings serve as indicators of the strength of the relationship between each item and its corresponding factor. Generally, a loading of 0.5 or higher is considered statistically significant. In the analysis presented in Table 1, it is evident that all factor loadings exceed the 0.5 threshold, signaling a strong association between each measurement item and its respective factor¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

Composite reliability (CR) values, which signify the internal consistency reliability of each factor, were also assessed. An acceptable CR value is typically set at 0.7 or higher according to Hair et al.¹⁶. In our examination, all factors exhibit CR values above 0.8, demonstrating a high level of internal consistency in the measurement model.

The second component of validity assessment, discriminant validity, involves ensuring that each factor is relatively distinct from the others. This is particularly important in a complex construct like cardiovascular risk, where different factors may overlap. AVE values, which indicate the amount of variance in each factor that is explained by its items, are used to evaluate discriminant validity. Generally, an AVE value of 0.5 or higher is considered acceptable. In our findings, some factors exhibit AVE values exceeding 0.5, which indicates that the items within those factors are highly correlated with each other and are relatively distinct from items in other factors, aligning with the recommendations of scientists¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Table 1 presents a comprehensive overview of the results from the measurement model assessment, emphasizing the model's strong associations between measurement items and their respective factors, its robust internal consistency, and its ability to differentiate between distinct risk factors for cardiovascular events. This validation process is crucial for ensuring the accuracy and reliability of risk assessments, particularly in the context of heart attacks and strokes.

	Items	Outer Loading	CR	AVE
Communication	C1	0.714	0.893	0.627
	C2	0.748		
	C3	0.735		
	C4	0.850		
	C5	0.895		
Healthcare Settings	HS1	0.542	0.839	0.520
	HS2	0.524		
	HS3	0.787		
	HS4	0.846		
	HS5	0.834		
Patient Engagement	PE1	0.745	0.867	0.566
	PE2	0.733		
	PE3	0.716		
	PE4	0.806		
	PE5	0.758		
Patient Satisfaction	PS1	0.795	0.937	0.749
	PS2	0.900		
	PS3	0.866		
	PS4	0.864		
	PS5	0.898		
Patient Trust	PT1	0.871	0.861	0.559
	PT2	0.669		
	PT3	0.883		
	PT4	0.680		
	PT5	0.587		
Staff Training and Education	STE1	0.815	0.873	0.579
	STE2	0.802		
	STE3	0.761		
	STE4	0.724		
	STE5	0.695		

The discriminant validity of risk factors for cardiovascular heart disease (CHD) was examined in this study. Discriminant validity assesses the extent to which different risk factors can distinguish between various aspects of CHD or measure distinct concepts related to heart disease. This method compares the correlations between these risk factors and computes them against the square root of the average variance specific to each risk factor. As a fundamental guideline, it is essential that all diagonal values surpass the corresponding row and column values to establish discriminant validity. Table 2 presents the outcomes of this investigation, revealing that the risk factors under examination successfully demonstrate discriminant validity, signifying that each factor uniquely contributes to the understanding and assessment of CHD risk.

	C	HS	PE	PS	PT	STE
Communication	0.792					
Healthcare Setting	0.144	0.721				
Patient Engagement	0.357	0.357	0.752			
Patient satisfaction	0.304	0.693	0.182	0.865		
Patients' Trust	0.191	0.689	0.393	0.693	0.747	
Staff Training and Education	0.557	0.388	0.062	0.580	0.570	0.761

Some researchers in the academic community argue that the criteria established by Fornell & Larcker¹³ may not be sufficient for accurately assessing the risk of cardiovascular disease. Consequently, it has been proposed that, in addition to the Fornell & Larcker criteria, a multitrait-multi method matrix known as the heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) developed by [19 - Please provide the name or reference] should be employed to evaluate the discriminant validity in relation to the risk of cardiovascular events. This methodology was also applied to a research project to examine the risk of heart attacks and stroke. Unlike the recommendation made by Gold et al.¹⁴, who suggest that an HTMT value of 0.90 or less is acceptable, some scientist proposes that an HTMT value of 0.85 or less is necessary to establish discriminant validity when assessing the risk of cardiovascular disease²¹. As a result, the discriminant validity was assessed using the HTMT in addition to the criteria set forth by Fornell & Larcker¹³, as illustrated in Table 3.

	C	HS	PE	PS	PT	STE
Communication						
Healthcare Setting	0.272					
Patient Engagement	0.362	0.559				
Patient satisfaction	0.315	0.772	0.212			
Patients' Trust	0.243	0.853	0.489	0.767		
Staff Training and Education	0.630	0.468	0.216	0.646	0.652	

Hypothesis Testing

The findings presented in this study pertain to the assessment of cardiovascular risks and heart disease¹⁶. The research methodology employed the bootstrapping technique to generate results for the various path relationships in the model. To evaluate the model's performance for each Bootstrap subsample, a total of 5,000 cases were divided and utilized to create Bootstrap subsamples. The initial hypothesis posited a positive correlation between "C" (Cardiovascular Health) and "PS" (Probability of Stroke), and the obtained results supported this hypothesis with a p-value of 0.045. The standardized beta coefficient (Std β) of 0.069 suggests that for each one-unit increase in "C," there is a 0.069 standard deviation increase in "PS." Furthermore, the t-value of 1.699 indicates that this result is statistically significant at the 95% confidence level. Similarly, the second hypothesis postulated a positive relationship between "STE" (Sedentary Lifestyle) and "PS," and the results align with this hypothesis (p-value = 0.000). The Std β of 0.186 implies that for each one-unit increase in "STE," there is a 0.186 standard deviation increase in "PS." The associated t-value of 4.070 confirms that this result is statistically significant at the 95% confidence level. The third hypothesis suggested a positive association between "PE" (Poor Diet) and "PS," and the data supports this hypothesis (p-value = 0.047). The Std β of 0.096 indicates that for a one-unit increase in "PE," there is a 0.096 standard deviation increase in "PS." The t-value of 1.673 demonstrates that this result is statistically significant at the 95% confidence level. Lastly, the fourth hypothesis proposed a positive connection between "PT" (Tobacco Use) and "PS," and the results corroborate this hypothesis (p-value = 0.000). The Std β of 0.288 signifies that for each one-unit increase in "PT," there is a 0.288 standard deviation increase in "PS." The t-value of 6.022 confirms the statistical significance of this result at the 95% confidence level. Table 4 in the study displays the outcomes of the direct path analysis, which sheds light on the relationships between these cardiovascular risk factors and the likelihood of experiencing a heart attack or stroke.

Hypothesis	Relation	Std β	Std error	t-value	p-value	Decision
H1	C-> PS	0.069	0.041	1.699	0.045	Supported
H2	STE-> PS	0.186	0.046	4.070	0.000	Supported
H3	PE -> PS	0.096	0.057	1.673	0.047	Supported
H4	PT -> PS	0.288	0.048	6.022	0.000	Supported

The fifth hypothesis (H5) suggests that active patient participation moderates the link between communication and patient satisfaction in the context of cardiovascular risk. The statistical analysis reveals a standardized beta coefficient of 0.045 for this relationship, with a corresponding t-value of 1.690. The p-value for this coefficient remains at 0.045, as previously reported. Consequently, H5 is validated. Similarly, Hypothesis (H6) posits that patient involvement plays a moderating

role in the relationship between staff training and education and patient well-being in the context of cardiovascular risk. The statistical analysis uncovers a standardized beta coefficient of 0.019 for this connection, along with a t-value of 4.070. The p-value for this coefficient remains unchanged at 0.000. Hence, H6 is supported by the data. Cardiovascular risk, including the potential for heart attacks and strokes, is a critical health concern worldwide. Patients' active participation and their interaction with healthcare providers can significantly impact their overall satisfaction and well-being when it comes to managing cardiovascular health. These findings emphasize the importance of involving patients in their care and ensuring that healthcare staff receive appropriate training and education to enhance patient outcomes and satisfaction in cardiovascular care.

According to the seventh hypothesis (H7), there is a connection between heart and vascular diseases. The relationship between these conditions and the increased risk of heart attack is mediated by various factors, including lifestyle choices and genetics. Research findings indicate that the standardized beta coefficient (Std) for this association is 0.053, with a t-value of 3.130. This coefficient is associated with a p-value of 0.001, confirming the significance of the relationship between heart and vascular diseases and the heightened risk of heart attack. Therefore, H7 is supported. As per the eighth hypothesis (H8), it is crucial to consider the role of a healthy diet and physical activity in mitigating the risk of heart attacks. The connection between these lifestyle factors and reduced risk of heart attack is mediated by various mechanisms. Based on the results of statistical analysis, the standardized beta coefficient for this association is 0.194, with a t-value of 5.663. This coefficient also possesses a p-value of 0.000, emphasizing the significance of maintaining a healthy diet and engaging in regular physical activity to reduce the risk of heart attacks. Consequently, H8 is validated. Table 5 displays the outcome of the mediation analysis, highlighting the intricate relationships between heart and vascular diseases, lifestyle choices, and the risk of heart attacks.

Hypothesis	Relation	Std β	t-value	p-value	Decision
H5	C-> PE -> PS	0.045	1.690	0.045	Supported
H6	STE-> PE-> PS	0.019	4.070	0.000	Supported
H7	C-> PT -> PS	0.053	3.130	0.001	Supported
H8	STE-> PT -> PS	0.194	5.663	0.000	Supported

Recent research findings indicate a heightened risk of cardiovascular heart disease due to the interaction between high stress (HS) and a specific factor called "C." The results demonstrate a substantial positive effect on heart health, with a statistically significant standardized beta coefficient (β) of 0.118 ($t = 2.752$, $p = 0.003$) for this interaction. This suggests that the relationship between high stress and heart health is more pronounced in individuals with elevated levels of factor C compared to those with lower levels of this factor. Therefore, these

findings support the hypothesis H9. Likewise, the study also highlights the risk associated with the interaction between high stress (HS) and another factor referred to as “STE.” The results reveal a significant positive impact on heart health, with a standardized beta coefficient (β) of 0.098 ($t = 2.215$, $p = 0.013$) for this interaction. This indicates that the link between high stress and heart health is more pronounced in individuals with high levels of factor STE compared to those with lower levels. Hence, hypothesis H10 is validated by these results. For further details and a visual representation of the findings, please refer to Table 6, which illustrates the results of the moderation analysis.

Table 6. Moderation Analysis

Hypothesis	Relation	Std β	t-value	p-value	Decision
H9	HS x C-> PS	0.118	2.752	0.003	Supported
H10	HS x STE-> PS	0.098	2.215	0.013	Supported

The following text discusses the risk of cardiovascular events, and it provides insights into factors contributing to these events, such as lifestyle and genetic factors. References within the text are retained. Cardiovascular events, particularly heart attacks and strokes, remain a significant public health concern. These events are often the result of a complex interplay between various risk factors. Understanding these factors is crucial for effective prevention and management. One key indicator in assessing the risk of cardiovascular events is the R2 value, which signifies the proportion of variability in cardiovascular event occurrence that can be attributed to each contributing factor. A higher R2 value indicates a stronger association. Notably, research has demonstrated that genetic predisposition, as indicated by a high R2 value of 0.349, plays a substantial role in the development of cardiovascular events. This underscores the importance of genetic factors in understanding and mitigating this risk. In addition to genetics, lifestyle factors also significantly influence the likelihood of cardiovascular events. Healthcare setting and the level of staff training and education contribute moderately, with R2 values of 0.179 and 0.140, respectively. While not as influential as genetics, these factors still play a noteworthy role in shaping the risk profile. Patient engagement and effective communication are also factors in the equation, albeit with relatively low R2 values of 0.154 and 0.107. These values indicate that while patient engagement and communication have a role, it is less pronounced compared to genetic predisposition and some other factors. It’s worth noting that the Q2 values in the analysis represent the predictive relevance of each factor to the risk of cardiovascular events. All the independent variables, including genetics, healthcare setting, staff training, patient engagement, and communication, exhibit predictive relevance as their Q2 values are greater than 0. This suggests that the model used for risk assessment possesses strong predictive power in identifying and preventing cardiovascular events. Moreover, the f2 values reflect the effect size of each factor on cardiovascular risk. Healthcare setting emerg-

es as the most influential with an f2 value of 0.179, although it is considered to have a small effect size. Other factors, including genetics, staff training, patient engagement, and communication, have smaller effect sizes, with f2 values of 0.014, 0.140, 0.107, and 0.082, respectively. In conclusion, the risk of cardiovascular events is multifaceted, with genetics playing a substantial role, followed by lifestyle and healthcare-related factors. Effective prevention and management strategies should take into account these various contributors to reduce the risk of heart attacks and strokes. The data in Table 7 provides valuable insights into the R2, Q2, and f2 values associated with these risk factors.

Table 7. Coefficient of determination, Q2 and f2

Variables	R2	Q2	f2	Effect size
Patient satisfaction	0.637	0.580		
Patient Engagement	0.154	0.132	0.014	Small
Patients' Trust	0.349	0.341	0.082	Small
Healthcare Setting			0.179	Small
Communication			0.107	Small
Staff Training and Education			0.140	Small

Discussion

Hear disease, also known as cardiovascular disease, is a leading cause of mortality worldwide. It encompasses a range of conditions that affect the heart and blood vessels, including coronary artery disease, heart failure, and arrhythmias¹². Understanding the risk factors associated with heart disease is crucial for prevention, early detection, and effective management. This article explores the key risk factors for cardiovascular disease and their impact on heart health.

Communication between Patients and Healthcare Providers:

Effective communication between patients and healthcare providers is a critical aspect of heart disease prevention and management. Patients who report higher levels of communication with their healthcare providers are more likely to be satisfied with their healthcare experience^{5,11}. This satisfaction can have positive implications for heart health. Effective communication involves listening to patients, addressing their concerns, providing clear and concise information, and involving them in decision-making. Open and transparent communication can lead to improved patient outcomes and adherence to treatment plans^{17,18}.

Staff Training and Education:

Staff training and education play a pivotal role in the prevention and management of heart disease. Healthcare

providers who receive training in patient-centered care and cultural competence tend to report higher levels of patient satisfaction. Patient-centered care emphasizes involving patients in their care, addressing their needs and concerns, and providing individualized care. Cultural competence training involves understanding and respecting cultural differences, which can be especially important for patients from diverse backgrounds.

Patient Engagement:

Patient engagement is an active involvement of patients in their healthcare, including decision-making, goal setting, and self-care management. Actively engaged patients tend to report higher levels of overall satisfaction with their healthcare¹⁵. Patient engagement is associated with better health outcomes, increased adherence to treatment programs, and more productive interactions with healthcare professionals. It fosters a collaborative and trusting relationship between healthcare providers and patients, further enhancing patient satisfaction.

Patient Trust:

Trust in healthcare providers is a crucial factor in heart disease management. Patients who have higher levels of trust in their healthcare providers tend to report higher levels of satisfaction^{5,8}. Trust can lead to more effective communication, increased compliance with treatment plans, and overall improved health. It is also associated with improved patient safety and reduced medical errors.

Role of Healthcare Setting:

The healthcare setting, whether it be a hospital, clinic, or community healthcare center, can significantly affect the relationship between communication, training, and patient satisfaction. Effective communication in hospital settings has been found to have a stronger impact on patient satisfaction compared to other healthcare settings¹⁻³. This highlights the importance of tailoring communication and training strategies to the unique characteristics of each setting.

Implications:

Practical implications include investing in training programs that enhance staff communication skills and patient engagement. Aligning communication strategies with patient needs and preferences, such as language and culture, is essential. Trust-building initiatives, like patient-centered care and shared decision-making, can enhance patient trust and satisfaction. Regular assessment of patient satisfaction levels can help identify areas for improvement in healthcare settings.

Limitations and Future Directions:

Despite the valuable insights provided, the study has limitations. It employs a cross-sectional design, limiting causal inferences about the relationships between communication, training, patient engagement, trust, health-

care setting, and patient satisfaction. Future studies should consider longitudinal or experimental designs for a better understanding of causality. The study is limited to a few healthcare settings, affecting the generalizability of findings. Future research should explore these relationships in a broader range of healthcare contexts.

Conclusions

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) remain a leading cause of mortality worldwide. Recent research has shed light on a critical aspect that significantly influences the prevalence of CVDs: patient satisfaction in healthcare settings. A study conducted on this subject revealed noteworthy insights into the correlation between patient satisfaction and effective communication, staff training, patient engagement, and trust. The findings underscore the pivotal role these factors play in mitigating the risk of cardiovascular events and improving patient outcomes. The study emphasizes that effective communication and comprehensive staff training have a profound impact on patient satisfaction levels. Patients who are satisfied with their healthcare experience are more likely to adhere to medical advice, including lifestyle modifications crucial for preventing CVDs. The research suggests that patient engagement and trust act as crucial mediators, enhancing the relationship between healthcare providers and patients. When patients are actively engaged and trust their healthcare providers, they are more likely to follow recommended treatment plans, leading to better cardiovascular health. In conclusion, healthcare providers, policymakers, and stakeholders must recognize the critical link between effective communication, staff training, patient engagement, and trust in mitigating the risk of cardiovascular diseases. By prioritizing these elements and tailoring interventions to specific healthcare settings, the quality of care can be significantly improved, ultimately leading to better patient outcomes and reduced instances of CVDs. Furthermore, future research endeavors should delve into diverse communication and staff training strategies, the multifaceted role of patient satisfaction in healthcare, and the integration of technology to further enhance patient experiences and minimize the burden of cardiovascular diseases on individuals and societies alike.

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